
Managing other pests

Nitrogen fertilization and *Meloidogyne incognita* incidence in rice

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We examined the influence of different rates of sulfate of ammonia on *M. incognita* in a greenhouse experiment. Faro II (OS6) seeds were grown in autoclaved sandy loam soil in microplots (1.5 × 1 × 1 m). Each block was inoculated with 600 eggs and second-stage juveniles of *M. incognita* obtained from galled roots of *Celosia* sp.

Sulfate of ammonia treatments at 30 and 45 kg N/ha, and an unfertilized control were in a completely randomized block design with 3 replications. Data on emergence, seedling vigor, and plant height were taken. Roots were examined for galls

and processed for nematode recovery.

Plant performance in the fertilized plots was better (see table). Galling was less in plants that received 45 kg N/ha, and the galls obtained were much smaller. Nematode recovery from infected roots was highest in plants without fertilizer. Although plants were much taller at reduced N, seedling vigor was less. □

Effect of ammonium sulfate fertilizer on *M. incognita* in rice. Badeggi, Nigeria.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Seedling vigor ^a	Galling index ^b	Nematode recovery (no.)
No N	53.5	4	2.5	23.50
30 kg N/ha	48.0	3	0.5	16.10
45 kg N/ha	42.3	1.5	—	7.20
LSD (5%)	4.7	1.71		15.03

^aStandard evaluation system for rice. ^b0 = no galls, 5 = maximum galling.

Water management

Economizing irrigation through rice fallow cropping strategies

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Water needs of alternative crops (peanut, sunflower, and green gram) were evaluated in irrigated rice fallows of coastal Maharashtra in 1986. The area receives essentially monsoon rainfall (2,500-3,500 mm) Jun-Sep, with a characteristic rain-free period Oct-May.

Soil of the experimental plot was medium black, with 0.63% organic C, 12.68 kg P, and 157.7 kg K/ha. Peanut, sunflower, and green gram were sown the first week of Jan; rice was sown in mid-Dec and transplanted in late Jan. Recommended fertilizer, plant density, plant protection, and irrigation were adopted. Water used by different crops was recorded throughout growth. Water use efficiency (WUE) was based on yield and water utilized.

The rice crop needed 1,185 mm of water for a yield of 4.1 t/ha (see table). Peanut, sunflower, and green gram

required 612-775 mm less water than rice, a 53-65% water economy with WUE almost identical (2.92-3.49 kg/ha per mm) to that of rice. The gross return from 1 mm of irrigation was about 2.4 times greater with alternative crops. □

Water use by rice, peanut, sunflower, and green gram on the irrigated rice fallows. Ratnagiri, Maharashtra, India, 1986.

Crop	Yield (t/ha)	Gross returns ^a (\$/ha)	Water applied (mm)	Gross returns (\$/mm irrigation)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per mm)	Economy in irrigation water (mm)
Rice	4.1	788	1185	0.66	3.46	—
Peanut	2.0	923	572	1.60	3.49	612 (53)
Sunflower	1.5	692	430	1.60	3.49	755 (64)
Green gram	1.2	646	410	1.58	2.92	775 (65)

^aFrom grain or pod.

Farming systems

Effect of tillage on stem borer (SB) larvae carry-over in a rice - wheat rotation

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Little time is left after rice harvest to prepare land for sowing wheat. Farmers cultivate twice, broadcast wheat seed, and cover it with a tractor-drawn wooden plank. Zero tillage or direct drilling is being introduced to reduce production costs.

But zero tillage leaves intact the rice stubble that harbors hibernating *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *S. innotata*, and *Sesamia inferens* SB. The larvae carry over to the next rice crop. *Sesamia* sp. also attacks wheat, spring maize, and sugarcane.

We assessed the extent to which Basmati 370 rice stubble would remain in condition for infestation by hibernating SB larvae in four differently tilled wheat fields in 1984-85 and 1985-86. A 65-hp tractor and implements (cultivator, plank, rototiller, and seed drill) were used in tillage operations in 30- × 30-m plots at the adaptive research farm and on 3 farmers' fields. Stubble was collected from 4 randomly selected 3-m² areas of each tillage type — zero-tilled/direct-drilled; cultivator run twice followed by one planking; cultivator run three times followed by two plankings; rototiller once, cultivator

Effect of tillage on stubble destruction and rice SB larvae hibernation in wheat following rice.^a Sheikhpura, Pakistan.

Tillage operation	Stubble (no./3 m ²)	SB-infested stubble (%)	Larvae (no./stubble)	Destruction (%) of stubble
<i>1984-85</i>				
Zero-tilled ^b /direct-drilled	137 a	84 a	3.8 ab	0
Cultivator (2) + plank (1)	44 b	46 b	1.8 d	64
Cultivator (3) + plank (2)	26 c	5 d	0.7 ef	79
Rototiller (1) + cultivator (2) + plank (1)	1 e	0 e	0.0 f	99
<i>1985-86</i>				
Zero-tilled ^b /direct-drilled	138 a	83 a	2.9 be	0
Cultivator (2) + plank (1)	37 b	37 c	2.0 cd	70
Cultivator (3) + plank (2)	14 d	5 de	1.8 d	88
Rototiller (1) + cultivator (2) + plank (1)	0 e	0 e	0.0 f	99

^aFigures followed by common letters are not statistically different (95% level of confidence by DMRT). ^bNo land preparation carried out. Wheat seed directly drilled.

twice, and planking once. The stubble was dissected in the laboratory for number of SB larvae/ stubble.

Data reveal nearly 100% destruction of stubble and no hibernating SB larvae in the rototilled fields (see table).

Cultivating followed by planking was not as effective in stubble destruction, but its effectiveness increased with number of runs. Larvae infestation was highest in the stubble of zero-tilled/direct-drilled fields. □

Intercropping upland rice and Lamtoro in acid Red Yellow Podzolic soils

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We studied the interactions of four cultivars of Lamtoro *Leucaena leucocephala* with upland rice *Oryza sativa* cultivar Sentani in acid Red Yellow Podzolic soil during 1983-84 cropping season. The soil was classified Haplorthox - Paleudult, with a 0-27 cm clayey topsoil, with pH of 4.2, exchangeable Al+H and Ca+Mg 4.0 and 0.7 meq/100 g, and Al saturation 85%.

Three-month-old Lamtoro seedlings were planted in double hedgerows 2 m apart (see figure). Each double hedgerow was 50 cm apart, with 33.3 cm between plants. Triple superphosphate (TSP) at 200 kg/ha was applied at the bottom of the plant hole at planting. The plants were cut back to 30 cm above the ground 4 mo after planting

Planting arrangement of Lamtoro and upland rice. Sumatra, Indonesia, 1983-84.

and the biomass incorporated into the soil.

One month after cutting and incorporating Lamtoro, upland rice was interseeded at 25- × 25-cm spacing into the well-established Lamtoro rows. Then 200 kg TSP, 50 kg KCl, and 40 kg carbofuran/ha were applied at the bottom of the plant hole with rice seeds. Two additional cuttings of Lamtoro were made at 2-mo intervals after rice seeding.

The experiment with Lamtoro cultivars Peru, K-8, K-28, Gung, and control without Lamtoro was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Plot size was 5 × 5m.

After three cuttings, cumulative dry weight of biomass of Peru was 4.6 t, Gung 4.7 t, K-8 5.2t, K-28 6.3 t/ha (see table). However, the interactions between upland rice and Lamtoro did not appear to favor upland rice growth